

RESPONSE PAPER

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FIRST NAME: Etienne

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA 401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 01

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Evidence-based policy (Austin 2007, 12-16)
2. PERI (Austin 2007, 24)
3. Multiple factors (Austin 2007, 31-34)
4. Externality (Austin 2007, 40)
5. Complex causality (Austin 2007, 51-55)
6. Retrospective cohort (Austin 2007, 61-64)
7. AFM (Austin 2007, 73)

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ACADEMIC ASSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academy essay writing is a process that must follow defined steps and comply with the guiding principles provided by the academic institution. In this response paper, I discussed the process of writing an academic essay from the planning stage to the submission of the final document. We also discussed avoiding plagiarism, style guidance, and the Chicago Manual of Style which is recommended by Euclid University. I learned that in addition to the prior knowledge of the topic before starting to write, dedicating enough time is also a requirement for the writing process.

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2) ESSAY WRITING

Among many types of existing essays, the academic essay discussed in period one of the ACA-402D coursepack is typically characterized by presenting facts to fulfill academic duties; this exercise follows a pre-established sequence of steps aiming to add more knowledge to the current literature field. For achieving good essays, writers are

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advised to make proper preparatory steps where enough time is dedicated to searching and digesting information related to the topic, understanding the questions, attempting answers, and making plans for guiding the writing process (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

The stage that follows understanding the topic consists of researching the content of the writings. It is done by collecting facts existing in [the](#) literature that provide answers to questions that are being studied. There are four questions that the reader should consider for this step: 1) what does the writer know about the topic? 2) What does the writer need to read and know to write the essay? 3) is the material useful to the argument? And 4) Can the writer use the material to support the answer? (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8). The authors provide useful advice:

“It is essential to make notes while you read..., and highlight relevant information, which you can return to when you re-read and make notes”.

The writers should not be limited by the sources of information, but it is a requirement to keep bibliographic details for information gathered during this stage because it will be used in the essay to avoid plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8).

Organizing ideas is based on making a good plan and putting acquired knowledge from the previous step on paper. The authors advise making plans based on the following factors:

1. To decide what could be the answers to the subject being studied
2. Selecting information that will support the answers
3. Using existing examples in the literature
4. Writing the above on a draft

The essay draft should have three sections: the introduction, body, and conclusion. In the introduction, we talk about the topic, [give](#) a little bit of the answer, and give a summary of the [essay's](#) contents. With the support of multiple paragraphs, we should use the body to answer the questions while demonstrating our knowledge of the matter and supporting our arguments with examples (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10).

Referencing the essay follows the style recommended by the institution. The final editing is crucial for making a good quality [essay](#), the recommendation that was given of keeping aside the draft for days before the final editing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11) did not work for me. Every time I put the draft aside for future [editing](#), I would be taken away by other office duties and could not complete [it](#).

Essay writing follows a very well-established stepwise process; [it](#) is very important to [follow](#) those steps to read as much as possible about the topic and dedicate enough time [to](#) editing. I liked how the writers are warned about procrastination from the very first pages of the documents (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). As my first experience, I experienced conflicting agendas and needed to dedicate more time to complete my first assignment.

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However, this taught me lessons on how to organize my time and work extra hours to allow me to deliver at my workplace and achieve my academic goals.

3) PLAGIALISM

Plagiarism is any situation where a writer uses information collected from different sources and avoids giving credit to the author of the information. This included using other people's words and ideas. Writers are warned by having someone write papers for them, and they submit it as if it is their own work. Plagiarism is unethical and jeopardizes other people's work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

Authors avoid plagiarism by providing sources of information and authors. In-text citations and the list of works cited are two main ways of giving credit to the authors of information used when writing an essay. An in-text citation is made by indicating the name of the authors, the year of publication, and the pages where the information was collected from. Everything is presented inside the parenthesis (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34-35).

Using this method of citation goes with quoting what the authors said using quotation marks, or the writer uses his or her own words, which is called paraphrasing. When using quotes, attention should be paid to formatting long quotations differently; long quotations do not go into quotation marks; instead, they are indented and look like separate little paragraphs (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 35).

4) STYLE GUIDE AND WHY WE NEED ONE

Style guides provide big lines to be followed by writers so that there is a standardized writing style for a specific industry or publication house. Correct punctuation and grammar are denominators of all writing styles. Writing styles provide standards for other aspects of writing that include preferred sentence length, text layout, font, and use of abbreviations, among others (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41). When it comes to freelancers, writing styles play a big role in measuring their capacity to comply with the publication house writing style. There is room for creative writing without following any documented writing style. However, this has its limitations; for example, it would take a very long time to revise and publish a document edited with a freestyle method (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 42). I downloaded one of the examples provided in the coursework (the BBC News style guide). After reading it, I was pleased to understand why, regardless of the News presenters, all BBC News is very understandable to even people like me who started learning English in tertiary education.

5) CMS CRIB SHEET

Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) is one of the published writing styles for formatting books and research papers for publication. This chapter explained how to use

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abbreviations; for example, I learned from the general rules that it is not acceptable to begin a sentence with a lowercase abbreviation, that we should always find ways of rewriting sentences and avoid beginning a sentence with acronym, that honorific and initials can be used and that scholarly abbreviation can be used inside parenthetical comments (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44). Previously, in my writing, I used to put acronyms in parentheses for the first time; I am using them in the text, but this was something I copied from my supervisor. I did not know that it is a writing style recommended by the CMS. I am still yet to learn more about geographical terms like places and states. It is recommended to always spell out them, but when used like an adjective, it can be used as an abbreviation, this was somehow confusing; I think I need to see more examples of this.

The CMS crib sheet is a rich chapter that talks about many other style guides, which include guidance on how to use compound words, italics and quotation marks, numbers and quotations, Chicago page formats, endnotes and footnotes, headings and lists, and bibliography. I was happy to read about guidance on the above-mentioned aspects of writing because I used to be confused about them when writing. I did not know that well-documented guidelines existed for editing them.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATION AND EXPRESSIONS

When I saw the title of the chapter, "Latin abbreviations and expressions," the first thing I asked myself was if this chapter was needed under this course with curiosity. I started reading and realized that it was a very important chapter that contains expressions we use in our daily communication without paying attention to their origin. Sometimes, we can even misuse them because we do not understand their meaning. In fact, I learned that Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing and that in formal and technical writing, we should use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid confusion and misinterpretation to our readers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59).

7) CONCLUSION

This course provided me with an understanding of how to better plan for academic writing. The plan should have a timeline, and we should allocate enough time for each writing phase, including the initial phase of understanding the questions. I discovered that knowledge of English is not enough for effective writing; the course provided more understanding of why plagiarism is bad and how to avoid it. On the other hand, the chapter on style guide opened my eyes to how to standardize my writing skills. Actually, the skills gained with this course pack are not applicable to academic essay writing only; they are very useful for any other written communication. I have already started seeing improvements in my writing at my office (emails, reports, etc.), and I feel more confident that my subsequent essay will be better.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

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